

A COMPARISON OF TWO MEASUREMENT TECHNIQUES FOR DETERMINING THE 2D PERMEABILITY CHARACTERISTICS OF REINFORCING TEXTILES

E. Fauster^{1*}, H. Grössing², R. Schledjewski^{1,2}

¹Chair of Processing of Composites,
Department Polymer Engineering and Science,
Montanuniversität Leoben, Leoben, Austria,
Email: ewald.fauster@unileoben.ac.at, web page: www.kunststofftechnik.at/composites

²Christian Doppler Laboratory for High Efficient Composite Processing,
Montanuniversität Leoben, Leoben, Austria

Keywords: liquid composite molding, 2D permeability characterization,
optical permeameter, capacitive permeameter

ABSTRACT

Two commonly known techniques for 2D permeability characterization are investigated in terms of sources for systematic deviations inherent to permeability results obtained: an optical and a capacitive permeability characterization system. The analysis addresses three major areas of deviations: (1) the mechanical nature of the molds, (2) the operation principle of the sensors and (3) the data evaluation algorithms. This paper focuses on an analysis of the data evaluation algorithms in terms of the elliptic geometry modelling techniques involved in the two systems.

1 INTRODUCTION

In liquid composite molding (LCM), dry preforms of reinforcing fabrics are placed in a mold and then impregnated with the liquid polymer matrix material. The impregnation process plays a key role as insufficiently saturated regions directly affect the mechanical properties of the final component. In order to avoid elaborate and expensive impregnation trials, filling simulations can be accomplished. These simulations strongly rely on accurate and trustworthy permeability values.

A well-established approach for characterizing the 2-dimensional permeability of reinforcing fabrics is based on radial flow experiments. There, a three-stage procedure is followed: (1) acquisition of specific sensor data during the actual experiment, where the fluid flow front shows a general elliptic shape, (2) evaluation of the sensor data to determine the timely advancement of the flow front and (3) calculation of the 2D permeability values from these characteristics following a specific mathematical algorithm. In this work, two different approaches for capturing the 2-dimensional flow front advancement characteristics of radial flow experiments are compared.

The optical approach on the one hand relies on a camera system focusing on the reinforcing fabric, which is positioned in a cavity with an optically transparent mould half. Sets of measurements along the flow front are then extracted by means of adequate digital image processing techniques. The capacitive measurement approach on the other hand involves a set of eight linear capacitive sensors, which are oriented in a star-like scheme around the central injection opening. The sensors capture a dielectric entity which increases linearly with the fluid covering the sensitive sensor area during the experiment. The flow front is finally reconstructed by approximation or interpolation of the data points with an elliptic geometric model.

In this paper, the authors identify and analyze major sources for systematic deviations inherent to the results gained with these two permeability characterization techniques.

2 2-DIMENSIONAL PERMEABILITY CHARACTERIZATION

A well-known approach to determine 2-dimensional permeability values of reinforcing fabrics is based on observation of radial flow experiments as introduced by Adams et al. [1–4]. There, the flow front of the saturated fabric is captured by means of specific sensor technology resulting in a set of data points for each instant of time during the experiment.

By application of interpolation or approximation techniques, respectively, the overall shape of the flow front is then reconstructed in terms of an elliptic geometric model. Evaluating the ellipse major and minor axes lengths over the entire length of the experiment results in the timely flow front characteristics.

Calculation of the in-plane permeability values from these characteristics [5] finally follows a specific mathematical algorithm. Adams and Rebenfeld [4] presented an algorithm, which is based on an iterative numerical solution for the degree of anisotropy, i.e. the ratio of the two principal planar permeability values. Chan and Hwang [6] on the contrary described an approach which introduces a transformation of the anisotropic problem into an equivalent isotropic system (EIS). Thereby, the second-order differential equation simplifies to the Laplace equation [5,7,8], for which a closed form solution exists. The resulting isotropic permeability is finally transformed back to the anisotropic system in order to obtain the desired permeability values.

Figure 1 shows an overview of the permeability characterization procedure together with the major sources of systematic deviations inherent to the results gained with an optical and a capacitive permeameter system.

Figure 1: Flow diagram representing the permeability characterization procedure together with major sources for systematic deviations inherent to results gained with the two permeameter systems.

3 TESTRIG DESCRIPTION

3.1 Optical Permeameter System

Figure 2 shows a picture of the optical test rig used in this paper. The frame of the test rig is set up by standard aluminum profiles. Directly on top of the working table, the metal mold half is mounted. The security glass plate forming the upper mold half is made from two glass plates, each 19mm in thickness, separated by a 0.76mm thin polymer foil. The glass mold half is framed with metal profiles in order to connect it to a hinge system on the back side of the test rig. A pneumatic cylinder finally provides for the flapping motion.

The actual mold cavity is specified through the cavity frame showing an inner dimension of 300mm x 400mm. After placing the reinforcing structures inside the cavity, the mold is closed by flapping the glass plate into a horizontal position. In addition, the glass plate is tightened with the lower mold half using a metal clamping frame and a set of screws. The radial flow experiment is then executed by injecting the test fluid into the cavity through a central injection point in the metal bottom mold half.

Figure 2: Optical permeability measurement system used for the radial flow experiments.

At a distance of about 1m above the mold, a camera system consisting of an industrial monochrome camera and a precision lens with a focal length of 16mm is mounted. The camera is used to acquire an image sequence during the radial flow experiment at an acquisition rate of up to 50fps at a resolution of 1392 x 1040 pixels. In order to determine the timely advancement of the fluid flow front, the sequence images are evaluated by means of a digital image processing algorithm specifically developed for this application [9]. The algorithm results in an elliptical geometry model (see Figure 3). Thus, the timely flow front advancement is finally obtained in terms of the major and minor axes length characteristics, respectively.

3.2 Capacitive Permeameter System

The capacitive measurement system, designed and manufactured by PMB – Präzisionsmaschinenbau Bobertag GmbH (www.pmb-bobertag.de), involves two metal mould halves, each being 150mm thick, mounted to a hydraulic press or mould carrier taking on the load resulting from preform compaction and fluid injection. A set of eight linear capacitive sensors is embedded in the lower mould half (see Figure 4, left) in a star-like scheme around the central injection point, whereas the test fluid is injected through a central injection opening in the upper mould half.

Figure 3: Example image of a radial flow experiment (top left) acquired with the optical permeameter and evaluation steps of the digital image processing algorithm (clockwise order).

Figure 4: Lower mould half of the capacitive permeameter with eight linear capacitive sensors (left) and mounting of the two mould halves in a hydraulic press (right).

The sensors show a length of 185mm (East and West sensors) and 105mm (all other sensors) as well as a sensitive width of 5mm. They capture the change of capacitive equivalent representing the dielectric properties of the material covering their sensitive areas. The flow front position is linearly related with the level of sensor saturation and thus, can be reconstructed from the sensor signals. The methodology was developed and patented by the Institut für Verbundwerkstoffe GmbH [10]. Applying data interpolation or approximation algorithms to the set of eight sensor values allows for the reconstruction of an elliptical geometry model describing the shape of the flow front. Again, the timely flow front advancement is finally obtained in terms of the major and minor axes length characteristics, respectively.

4 GEOMETRIC FLOW FRONT MODELLING

As is well known, ellipses are a member of the family of conic sections, who can be described by means of the general equation of quadratic forms:

$$c'_1x^2 + c'_2xy + c'_3y^2 + c'_4x + c'_5y + c'_6 = 0, \quad (1)$$

with the set of conic parameters $\{c'_1, \dots, c'_6\}$. This can be rewritten as a matrix equation:

$$\mathbf{p}^T C \mathbf{p} = 0, \quad (2)$$

with the vector of homogeneous point coordinates $\mathbf{p} = [x, y, 1]^T$ and the conic matrix:

$$C = \begin{bmatrix} c'_1 & \frac{c'_2}{2} & \frac{c'_4}{2} \\ \frac{c'_2}{2} & c'_3 & \frac{c'_5}{2} \\ \frac{c'_4}{2} & \frac{c'_5}{2} & c'_6 \end{bmatrix}. \quad (3)$$

Note that the conic parameters are homogeneous, i.e. they are defined only up to a non-zero scale. Thus, we can multiply with $\frac{1}{c'_6}$ and obtain:

$$c_1x^2 + c_2xy + c_3y^2 + c_4x + c_5y = -1. \quad (4)$$

Obviously, the conic coefficients c_i are related to the five parameters describing an ellipse in general location: c_1 and c_3 refer to the semi-major and semi-minor ellipse axis lengths, respectively, c_4 and c_5 relate to the center point coordinates and c_2 refers to the orientation angle. Details on Euclidean classification of conics as well as a derivation of ellipse parameters from the set of conic parameters are well reported in literature, e.g. by Gallier [11].

4.1 Interpolating an Elliptic Geometry Model to a Given Set of Data Points

In order to determine the parameters of the interpolating ellipse to a given set of data points, we can formulate a system of n equations linear in the n conic parameters being sought. Therein, n denotes the number of degrees of freedom (DoF) of the ellipse, either being 2 (ellipse with axes coinciding with the coordinate axes), 3 (ellipse centered at the point of origin) or 5 (ellipse in general location). This system of equations can then be briefly rewritten as a matrix equation:

$$A_n \mathbf{c} = \mathbf{b}, \quad (5)$$

with the vector $\mathbf{c} = [c_1, \dots, c_6]^T$ of conic parameters being sought, the vector of inhomogeneous coefficients $\mathbf{b} = -\mathbf{1}_n$ ($\mathbf{1}_n$ being a vector of 1's and length n) and an $n \times n$ design matrix A_n specifically composed for the distinct interpolation task.

Equation (5) can be solved for the vector of conic parameters \mathbf{c} by means of well-known solution strategies for systems of linear equations, such as the Gaussian elimination method.

4.1.1 Interpolating an Ellipse Centered at the Origin to a Set of Three Data Points

Given a set of three points $\mathbf{p}_1 = [x_1, y_1]^T$, $\mathbf{p}_2 = [x_2, y_2]^T$ and $\mathbf{p}_3 = [x_3, y_3]^T$, to which an interpolating ellipse centered at the point of origin is sought. We then can define the following system of equations (linear in the conic parameters being sought) for the three points on the ellipse:

$$\begin{aligned} c_1x_1^2 + c_2x_1y_1 + c_3y_1^2 &= -1, \\ c_1x_2^2 + c_2x_2y_2 + c_3y_2^2 &= -1, \\ c_1x_3^2 + c_2x_3y_3 + c_3y_3^2 &= -1. \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

The design matrix A_3 to be set up for solving this system of equations according to Equation (5) is then given as:

$$A_3 = \begin{bmatrix} x_1^2 & x_1 y_1 & y_1^2 \\ x_2^2 & x_2 y_2 & y_2^2 \\ x_3^2 & x_3 y_3 & y_3^2 \end{bmatrix}, \quad (7)$$

and we can solve for the vector of conic parameters $\mathbf{c} = [c_1, c_2, c_3, 0, 0, 1]^T$.

However, interpolation of an elliptic geometry model to data points, deteriorated by measurement noise, can lead to unwanted results. For a given set of three data points forming a concave curve with respect to the point of origin, the interpolation algorithm produces a set of conic parameters representing a hyperbolic solution rather than an ellipse. This situation can easily be detected by making use of the Euclidean invariants of the conic matrix given in Equation (3), see Gallier [11].

However, in order to force an elliptic solution, i.e. finding the conic parameters of an origin-centered ellipse, an approximation algorithm needs to be followed rather than an interpolation routine.

4.2 Approximating an Elliptic Geometry Model to a Given Set of Data Points

Given a set of n noisy data points $\mathbf{p}_i = [x_i, y_i]^T, i = [1..n]$, such as a set of points resulting from a measurement task, to which an elliptic geometry model is to be fitted. Mathematically, the task is described as a nonlinear least squares problem, which is given by minimizing the sum $\sum_{i=1}^n r_i^2$, with r_i representing data residuals, i.e. algebraic distances of the data points \mathbf{p}_i to the elliptic geometry model being sought. The residuals are defined by means of the general equation of quadratic forms:

$$c_1 x_i^2 + c_2 x_i y_i + c_3 y_i^2 + c_4 x_i + c_5 y_i + c_6 = r_i. \quad (8)$$

Collecting the system of equations for all data points, we obtain:

$$\sum_{i=1}^n r_i^2 = \mathbf{r}^T \mathbf{r} = (D\mathbf{c})^T D\mathbf{c} = \mathbf{c}^T D^T D\mathbf{c} = \mathbf{c}^T S\mathbf{c}, \quad (9)$$

with the vector of residuals $\mathbf{r} = [r_1, \dots, r_n]^T$, the vector $\mathbf{c} = [c_1, \dots, c_6]^T$ of ellipse parameters being sought and the $n \times 6$ design matrix D :

$$D = \begin{bmatrix} x_1^2 & x_1 y_1 & y_1^2 & x_1 & y_1 & 1 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots \\ x_n^2 & x_n y_n & y_n^2 & x_n & y_n & 1 \end{bmatrix}. \quad (10)$$

The vector \mathbf{c} of ellipse parameters is finally found by means of singular value decomposition [12] of the scatter matrix $S = D^T D$ or by even more efficient solution strategies, such as the algorithm presented by Harker et al. [13].

Note that the approximation technique not only gives the vector of ellipse parameters being sought, but also delivers the actual algebraic distances of the data points to the geometry model. Thus, a quality measure of the approximation result can automatically be derived. Moreover, analysis of the algebraic distance values allows for an automatic detection and elimination of unreliable sensor data.

5 SYSTEM COMPARISON

5.1 Sources for Systematic Deviations

Following the permeability characterization procedure described in Section 2 together with the test rig descriptions in the previous section, there are a number of sources for systematic deviations in the permeability results gained with the two techniques. Table 1 gives an overview of the most relevant contributors.

	Optical Permeameter	Capacitive Permeameter
Mechanical Setup		
Lower mould half material	Steel, 40mm thick + Aluminum, 25mm thick	Aluminum, 150mm thick
Upper mould half material	Composite glass plate (19mm glass / 0.76mm polymer foil / 19mm glass)	Aluminum, 150mm thick
Load bearing mechanism	Stiffening frame, fastening screws	Hydraulic press
Sensorics		
Test fluid injection pressure	Pressure control valve	Pressure control valve, pressure sensor
Test fluid temperature (fluid viscosity)	Fluid thermometer (inline)	Fluid thermometer (offline)
Flow front detection	Industrial camera, 1392 x 1040 pixel	8 linear capacitive sensors in star-like orientation scheme
Data Evaluation		
Flow front modelling	n-point ellipse approximation	3-point ellipse interpolation
Permeability computation algorithm	Adams et al. [4] or Chan and Hwang [6]	Adams et al. [4]

Table 1: Overview of sources for systematic differences between the optical and capacitive permeameter system.

In the subsequent sections, the major sources for systematic deviations inherent to results gained with the two permeability characterization techniques are described in more detail. However, due to space limitations for this paper, the focus is put on an analysis of algorithms for modelling the flow front geometry by means of ellipse approximation and interpolation strategies, respectively.

5.2 Mechanical Nature of Permeameter Cavities

Considering the mechanical nature of the mould parameters listed in Table 1, the lower material stiffness of the composite glass plate forming the upper mould half of the optical permeameter stands out. Although required for the camera system focusing on the reinforcing material sample being saturated, the composite glass plate shows significantly lower structural bending stiffness than the full-metal mould of the capacitive permeameter. Thus, a stiffening frame is applied to support the composite glass plate and thus, minimizing mould deflection. The stiffening frame has been designed with the help of mechanical FEM simulations as a trade-off between maximizing structural bending stiffness and minimizing optical occlusion. The strategy of this design approach, the mechanical shape of the stiffening frame finally obtained as well as a study on the resulting mould deflection as a function of both, preform compaction pressure as well as fluid injection pressure, is presented in a paper recently submitted by the authors [14].

5.3 Test Fluid Properties

For experiments conducted with the two permeameters, commercially available plant oil is used. However, its viscosity depends on the temperature. As the fluid temperature changes due to daytime as well as seasonal impacts on the climatic laboratory conditions, the temperature-viscosity-dependency of the test fluid was determined by means of Couette rheometer measurements.

In order to provide accurate test fluid viscosity values for calculating the 2-dimensional permeability values, the fluid temperature needs to be measured prior or during the experiments. The optical permeameter system includes an inline fluid temperature sensor enabling automated interpolation into the temperature-viscosity-characteristics. The capacitive permeameter however, does not provide inline temperature measurement. Thus, offline fluid temperature measurements are required for experiments with this system.

Well comparable temperature measurement results can be guaranteed as the two thermometer devices were calibrated by means of reference measurements on an accurately heated fluid sample. Thus, unwanted impact of fluid viscosity values on the permeability calculation can be eliminated.

The two permeability characterization systems were equipped with identical types of pressure control devices. Furthermore, the structure (tubing and instruments) and length of the fluid injection lines on the systems are well comparable. As a result, unwanted impact of the test fluid injection pressure on the permeability values can be avoided.

5.4 Capturing Measurement Data on the Fluid Flow Front

In order to directly compare the accuracy of sensing the fluid flow front with the optical and capacitive permeameter systems, respectively, a specifically designed experiment was carried out, enabling the simultaneous capturing of the advancing flow front by the industrial camera system of the optical permeameter as well as the eight capacitive sensors of the capacitive permeameter. However, due to space limitations for this paper, details on the experiment and results obtained need to be skipped here.

5.5 Elliptic Geometry Model Fitting

As depicted in Figure 3, the digital image processing algorithm used to evaluate the acquired images in the optical permeameter setup is based on a three-step strategy:

1. derivation of a binary image covering the saturated preform area,
2. locating sets of data points along the fluid flow front, and
3. fitting of an elliptical geometry model to the sets of data points.

As a result of this approach, a specific number of n data points can be used for the geometry fitting step, whereas n increases with the progress of the fluid flow front.

The capacitive permeameter however, uses a set of eight linear capacitive sensors for capturing the flow front advancement. Thus, a number of eight data points is available for describing the flow front at each instant of time during the experiments. The proprietary software application provided by the manufacturer of the measurement system enables the user to select from 18 predefined sensor triple combinations - a triple being a set of three sensors, e.g. N (north), E (east) and SW (south-west) - for interpolating an elliptical geometry model centered to the point of fluid injection.

5.5.1 Experimental Work

A direct comparison of the geometry modelling strategies by incorporating the data acquired with the two permeability characterization systems is prevented as the nature of capturing the data is significantly different. However, in order to study the impact of the geometry modelling strategy on the permeability values, a modified experiment was conducted. The optical permeameter was used for an experiment on a tri-axial Carbon fiber NCF preform whereas the metal stiffening frame of the system was eliminated in order to capture sequence images of the entirely unveiled preform area. The experiment was done at 53.6% fiber volume content and 1.5bar fluid injection pressure.

As depicted at an exemplarily chosen sequence image in Figure 5, a set of data points along the fluid flow front was extracted, representing the basis for the n-point-approximation technique described in Section 4.2.

Figure 5: Example image acquired with the optical permeameter system (left) and data points extracted along the fluid front by digital image processing techniques (right).

However, this set of data points was further processed by an overlay of the sensitive areas of eight virtual linear sensors in a star-like scheme, just as in the capacitive permeameter (see Figure 6, left). After segmentation of the flow front data points covered by the particular virtual sensors, a center-of-gravity calculation is followed resulting in a set of eight virtual data points (Figure 6, right). These data points can now be used for further comparison purposes.

Figure 6: Overlay of virtual linear capacitive sensors to the image of the optical permeameter system (left) and extraction of the center-of-gravity point at the north-west virtual sensor (right).

In order to investigate the effect of the number of data points used for fitting the elliptic geometry model, the ellipse approximation algorithm presented by Harker et al. [13] was applied to (a) the full set of data points and (b) the set of eight virtual data points.

5.5.2 Evaluation Results

Executing this procedure for all sequence images acquired during the experiment gives the timely characteristics of flow front advancement in terms of the major and minor ellipse axes lengths, respectively. The results are depicted in Figure 7 and show little deviation in the general trends. However, the characteristics obtained by fitting to the eight virtual data points show a higher noise level, which is an obvious effect of the reduced number of data points.

Furthermore, the data evaluation schematic provided in the software of the capacitive permeameter was reflected in the analysis: 16 combinations of virtual data point triples (see last column of Table 2, the letters contained therein abbreviate cardinal directions along which the particular sensors are aligned) were extracted and provided for the ellipse interpolation algorithm described in Section 4.1., resulting in the timely characteristics of the flow front advancement for all of the configurations.

Actually, there are two more data evaluation configurations provided by the software of the capacitive permeameter. However, these are not included in this analysis as they are not directly based on measurement data gained from the sensors, but rather derived from these by averaging of data from pairs of opposing sensors.

Figure 7: Comparison of the timely flow front advancement characteristics obtained from fitting elliptical geometry models with the n-point- and 8-virtual-point-strategies, respectively.

Finally, the 2-dimensional permeability values were calculated from the timely flow front advancement characteristics obtained with (a) the n-point-approximation technique, (b) the 8-virtual-point-approximation technique and (c) the 3-virtual-point-interpolation method applied to all of the 16 sensor triple configurations. The permeability values were calculated with the algorithm of Adams et al. [4]. The results are listed in Table 2 together with relative difference values, where the permeability values obtained from the n-point-approximation technique were taken as reference values.

#	k_1 [m ²]	k_2 [m ²]	Δk_1 [%]	Δk_2 [%]	Remark
1	115,1E-12	59,9E-12	6,53	6,81	Sensors: N-E-NE
2	125,9E-12	57,3E-12	2,27	2,16	Sensors: N-E-NW
3	118,7E-12	58,4E-12	3,64	4,22	Sensors: N-E-SW
4	127,2E-12	57,2E-12	3,30	2,12	Sensors: N-E-SE
5	103,4E-12	60,0E-12	16,01	7,02	Sensors: N-W-NE
6	123,5E-12	55,1E-12	0,30	1,71	Sensors: N-W-NW
7	108,2E-12	58,5E-12	12,10	4,44	Sensors: N-W-SW
8	124,7E-12	54,9E-12	1,28	2,03	Sensors: N-W-SE
9	98,7E-12	59,5E-12	19,81	6,15	Sensors: S-W-NE
10	123,8E-12	53,3E-12	0,55	4,98	Sensors: S-W-NW
11	102,8E-12	58,1E-12	16,50	3,66	Sensors: S-W-SW
12	125,1E-12	53,2E-12	1,57	5,10	Sensors: S-W-SE
13	109,2E-12	59,2E-12	11,32	5,67	Sensors: S-E-NE
14	126,7E-12	55,1E-12	2,86	1,74	Sensors: S-E-NW
15	111,7E-12	57,8E-12	9,29	3,21	Sensors: S-E-SW
16	128,0E-12	55,2E-12	3,96	1,49	Sensors: S-E-SE
17	124,1E-12	57,7E-12	0,80	2,88	8-virtual-point-appr.
18	123,1E-12	56,0E-12	-	-	n-point-appr.

Table 2: Comparison of results gained with the n-point- and 8-virtual-point-approximation strategies.

Comparing the results from the n-point-approximation technique with the results of the 16 configurations of 3-virtual-point-interpolation strategy, one can clearly see that all configurations containing data of the virtual NW or SE sensors, i.e. the even configuration numbers, show significantly lower relative differences than most of the others. This can be explained by the

orientation of the elliptical flow front closely to the -45° direction as a result of the fiber orientations in the tri-axial NCF used for this analysis. The NW and SE sensors cover data points near the major vertex of the ellipse, giving a reliable basis for the 3-point-interpolation algorithm.

Most of the configurations not covering the NW and SE sensors show a relative difference in the permeability value k_1 of up to 20%. This value is in the range of uncertainty values typically reported [15–17] for 2-dimensional permeability values and clearly unacceptable to be caused by the evaluation algorithm of the permeability characterization system.

However, the even more important information from this analysis is the wide span of relative differences obtained with the data from the particular configurations of virtual sensors. This indicates that the user of the system needs to carefully select the sensor triple configurations when evaluating the measurement data in order to obtain meaningful data. For that purpose, a-priori-knowledge about the orientation of the fluid flow front is required.

Comparing the results from the n-point-approximation technique with those of the 8-virtual-point-approximation technique, rather small relative difference values can be observed. This indicates a major advantage of the 8-point-approximation technique over the 3-point-interpolation strategy. In addition to the higher reliability of the data, subjective system user decisions can be avoided as all of the available eight data points can automatically be used for the elliptic geometry model fitting.

6 SUMMARY, CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

The work presented in this paper addresses sources for systematic deviations inherent to results obtained with an optical and a capacitive permeability characterization system, respectively. Three major categories of sources were identified: (1) the mechanical nature of the test rig molds, (2) the operation principle of the sensors and (3) the data evaluation algorithms. Concentrating on the data evaluation part, the elliptical geometry modelling techniques were investigated in detail. Following a specifically designed radial flow experiment combined with the introduction of virtual sensors, a direct comparison of ellipse approximation and interpolation techniques was realized.

The results of the analysis clearly indicate the advantage of the ellipse approximation technique over the interpolation strategy in terms of: (a) higher reliability of the results obtained, (b) automatically generated information about the quality of the model fitting results and (c) avoiding unwanted impact due to subjective decisions of the system user when selecting the sensor triples.

Future work will address an extension of the analysis of systematic deviations inherent to the results gained with the two permeability characterization systems described in this paper according to the scheme in Figure 1.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

Ralf Schledjewski and Harald Grössing kindly acknowledge the financial support provided by the Federal Ministry of Science, Research and Economy in Austria and the FACC Operations GmbH.

REFERENCES

- [1] Adams KL, Rebenfeld L. Permeability characteristics of multilayer fiber reinforcements. Part I: Experimental observations. *Polymer Composites* 1991; 12(3):179–185.
- [2] Adams KL, Rebenfeld L. Permeability characteristics of multilayer fiber reinforcements. Part II: Theoretical model. *Polymer Composites* 1991; 12(3):186–190.
- [3] Adams KL, Rebenfeld L. In-Plane Flow of Fluids in Fabrics: Structure/Flow Characterization. *Textile Research Journal* 1987; 57(11):647–654.
- [4] Adams KL, Russel W, Rebenfeld L. Radial penetration of a viscous liquid into a planar anisotropic porous medium. *International Journal of Multiphase Flow* 1988; 14(2):203–215.
- [5] Bear J. *Dynamics of fluids in porous media*. New York: Dover; 1988.
- [6] Chan AW, Hwang S. Anisotropic in-plane permeability of fabric media. *Polymer Engineering and Science* 1991; 31(16):1233–1239.
- [7] Weitzenböck J, Sheno R, Wilson P. Measurement of three-dimensional permeability. *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing* 1998(29A):159–169.
- [8] Weitzenböck J, Sheno R, Wilson P. Radial flow permeability measurement. Part A: Theory. *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing* 1999; 30(6):781–796.
- [9] Fauster E, Grössing H, Schledjewski R. Uncertainty Analysis for Optical Permeability Measurement of Reinforcing Textiles. In: *Proceedings of ICCM 19, Montreal, 29.07.-02.08.2013*.
- [10] Daniel P, Kissinger C, Roeder G. Anordnung zur Vermessung der Ausbreitung eines Matrixmaterials in elektrisch leitfähigen Verstärkungsstrukturen: Arrangement for measuring the propagation of a matrix material in electrically conductive reinforcing structures: Google Patents; 2001; Available from: <https://www.google.com/patents/DE10004146C2?cl=en>.
- [11] Gallier JH. *Geometric methods and applications: For computer science and engineering*. New York: Springer; 2001.
- [12] Golub GH, van Loan CF. *Matrix computations*. 3rd ed. Baltimore: Johns Hopkins University Press; 1996.
- [13] Harker M, O’Leary P, Zsombor-Murray P. Direct type-specific conic fitting and eigenvalue bias correction. *Image and Vision Computing* 2008; 26(3):372–381.
- [14] Grössing H, Fauster E, Schledjewski R. Robust Two-Dimensional Optical Permeability Determination – Part A: Test Rig and Measurement System. *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*; submitted.
- [15] Liu Q, Parnas RS, Giffard HS. New set-up for in-plane permeability measurement. *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing* 2007; 38(3):954–962.
- [16] Hammond VH, Loos AC. The Effects of Fluid Type and Viscosity on the Steady State and Advancing Front Permeability Behavior of Textile Preforms. *Journal of Reinforced Plastics and Composites* 1997; 16(1):50–72.
- [17] Dunkers JP, Phelan FR, Zimba CG, Flynn KM, Sanders DP, Peterson RC et al. The prediction of permeability for an epoxy/E-glass composite using optical coherence tomographic images. *Polymer Composites* 2001; 22(6):803–814.